

Chagos and the British Indian Ocean Territory: A colonial anachronism in the post-colonial era

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Until the 1960s, Chagos was a little-known archipelago in a remote stretch of the Indian Ocean. Its nearest neighbour (Maldives) is more than 1000 kilometres away; it was, literally, a world apart. Uninhabited until the late-eighteenth century, people were brought in to work (originally as slaves) in the new coconut plantations. It was first claimed as a colony by France, until Napoleon lost control of his country's overseas possessions and, early in the nineteenth century, Britain stepped in. Little was heard of Chagos before the 1960s, when Britain allowed the United States to locate a new military base on the largest island, Diego Garcia. Since then, the once-remote islands – redesignated as the British Indian Ocean Territory – have rarely been out of the news. After a dispute extending over nearly six decades, Britain finally agreed to negotiate with Mauritius on a new future for what continues to be known as Chagos.

At this crucial juncture, answers are sought in this paper to some of the searching questions that surround the belated transition of Chagos from a colonial past to a post-colonial future. Why has Mauritius always been adamant that it is the 'rightful heir' to territory so far from its own capital? How important in this still-evolving sequence of events are the human rights of those who were forced to leave the islands? Where does the US sit in all of this, a tenant less likely to leave with every year that passes? And what about the unique environment of the mid-Indian Ocean: does this get a say when the spoils are divided or is it all about geopolitics?

The present situation is complicated by an unusually large dose of rhetoric. It is not just a question of former colonies (in a broad alliance supporting Mauritius), taking the opportunity to further discredit a system of control that is long past its time. There is also the highly-charged fact that those who had earlier been brought to the islands to work were then forcibly removed to enable not only the construction and operation of the military base on Diego Garcia, but also a *cordon sanitaire* on the surrounding islands. Emotion is never far from the surface; Chagos is no ordinary case of political history. While seeking to be as dispassionate as possible, I have found it impossible to be totally objective and to resist some commentary. In turn, readers, will of course, offer their own interpretation of events. Chagos, in many ways, can be seen as a vortex of contrasting views and claims, a swirl of ideologies where truth can all too easily be obscured.

Colonial legacy

Portuguese explorers, at the end of the sixteenth century, were the first Europeans to round the Cape of Good Hope and enter the Indian Ocean. They made landfall on some of the mid-ocean islands to replenish water supplies and fresh food, before continuing north-eastwards to establish a direct sea route to India. The Dutch, too, were early explorers, taking control of the large island of Mauritius (the name itself a reminder of that era) but their sights were also set on what lay beyond. In contrast, the French were avid colonists in the region, although some of their early possessions were soon lost to the British. Chagos was one such example, at first within French jurisdiction, a distant outpost administered as a matter of convenience from Mauritius.

The heyday of European colonial expansion was in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, with its demise becoming inevitable after the Second World War. The UN Charter was itself an important marker of legitimate rights of occupation and the principle of self-determination.¹ In due course, one former colony after another gained independence. Sovereignty, however, did not automatically bring prosperity and a legacy of resentment is embedded in post-colonial histories. The presence of multi-national corporations added to a sense that the former colonies were simply exchanging one form of control for another, and that income from their own resources would continue to seep away. Independence was not all that had been hoped for. All of this, and more, would later emerge in the lengthy hearings questioning Britain's control of the contested Chagos archipelago.²

Mauritius, as the claimant of sovereignty, achieved independence in 1968 and has constantly maintained that the failure to transfer Chagos at the same time rendered the handover incomplete. It was contended that, three years before independence, Britain unlawfully removed the archipelago from within the original boundaries of Mauritius. In fact, Britain went a stage further and redesignated the islands as the British Indian Ocean Territory, aptly described by one observer as 'the last colony'.³ At a time when one colony after another was becoming independent, Chagos was taken in the opposite direction. The reason for this was clear enough: so long as Britain retained control, it saw itself free to cede the use of Diego Garcia to its American allies for military purposes. Mauritius argued that it did not, in fact, have the legal right to do so and, eventually, the case for and against was heard in The Hague, in the International Court of Justice. The Court was not empowered to mandate an outcome but, rather, to offer an 'advisory opinion'. As such, when it convened in September 2018 there were two questions to answer:

Was the process of decolonization of Mauritius lawfully completed when Mauritius was granted independence in 1968, following the separation of the Chagos Archipelago from Mauritius?

*[And] what are the consequences under international law... with respect to the inability of Mauritius to implement a programme for the resettlement on the Chagos Archipelago of its nationals, in particular those of Chagossian origin.*⁴

The essence of the Mauritian argument was that, without the inclusion of Chagos (which had been part of the original colony), the process of decolonization remained unlawful. To add to the argument, it had been wrong, therefore, for the people living and working there to have been expelled. A programme for the resettlement of the exiled Chagossian population, it was asserted, should be initiated without delay. Britain, in turn, responded that it had acted lawfully and was not required to submit a dispute within its own jurisdiction to an external body for judgement, unless it consented to do so (which, of course, it did not). In due course, therefore, for several years after the court hearing was concluded, Britain refused to accept the validity of the outcome or take any action.

In addition to the two leading contenders, evidence was received from a wide range of other countries (most of which had no direct involvement in the issue), overwhelmingly in support of Mauritius. Chagos had become an international *cause célèbre* and, quite apart from the merits and demerits of the case, the hearing was seen as an opportunity to pronounce on the iniquities of colonialism. Some of the representatives of former colonies were quite open in their intentions. South Africa, for instance, saw it as nothing less than the duty of all members of the UN ‘to assist the general assembly to remove all the last vestiges of colonialism’.⁵ On behalf of Mauritius, the leading counsel, Philippe Sands (who, in fact, practiced in London), reminded the hearing that times had changed:

*... the right to self-determination is not a heritage issue. This is not Africa in the late-19th century or early 20th century. This is September 2018.*⁶

In the event, it was no surprise that there was an overwhelming majority in the subsequent UN Assembly in favour of Mauritius (116-6, with 56 abstentions).⁷ To add to the strength of the case, the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea would also rule against British occupation of Chagos (although that body, too, could not mandate its decision).⁸ In these ways, the moral case for Britain to withdraw was beyond question, but there was still no legal obligation to do so. If not formally required, however, the court of public opinion could not so easily be ignored and international pressure was undoubtedly exerted on Britain to concede. When seeking support for Ukraine in 2022, in the face of the Russian invasion of that country, Britain was asked by African countries how it could act in this way when it was itself illegally occupying another country.⁹ It was time for some judicious disentangling.

After earlier years of wrangling, it was left to Britain’s shortest-serving prime minister, Liz Truss, in late-2022, to request her foreign secretary to initiate negotiations that would cede

the territory to Mauritius. Inevitably, the US would be present in these talks, which, at the time of writing are still ongoing.¹⁰

Is it really about human rights?

In all the arguments for Britain to leave, a persistent point is that the human rights of the Chagossians were wilfully abused. It is an argument which cannot reasonably be countered, whether in the original period of slavery, followed by contract employment with a denial of land and housing rights, and, finally, expulsion.

First came the arrival of the French towards the end of the eighteenth century and the introduction in 1793 of slaves from Madagascar and East Africa, to work in the plantations producing copra for export. When the trade in slaves was abolished by the British soon after taking control of the colony of Mauritius, and the practice as a whole, across the British Empire, was consigned to the past in 1834, the status of the population of Chagos was changed to that of contract workers, without rights to own a house or land. Licences were granted for residency by the plantation owners, and workers were moved from island to island to meet company needs. This quasi-feudal system continued until a decision was taken, in secret, in the 1960s to lease Diego Garcia to the Americans and remove all of the inhabitants not only from that island but from the whole cluster. It is this action of displacement which has featured in recent years as an international human rights issue.

The forced expulsion of the Chagossians by the UK and US, and the refusal to allow them to return for the last 50 years is a stark example of an ongoing colonial crime, one that began in the 1960s, but which has continued into 2023. The colonial power, the UK, forcibly displaced an entire people, and has largely failed to acknowledge responsibility and provide an adequate remedy ever since.¹¹

The facts of the case speak for themselves. For security reasons – coupled with the less-publicized reality that the plantations were no longer thriving – all of the inhabitants were forcibly removed from the archipelago. The first to go were those who at the time were temporarily overseas (often for medical reasons) and were denied a return passage; followed by those living on Diego Garcia, in the path of the bulldozers; and, finally, the scattered population on the outer islands. Most of the exiles were taken to Mauritius, some went to Seychelles and, through a later concession, the rest to Britain. When, in 1965, the decision was taken to initiate this process, a sum of £3 million was paid to the government of Mauritius to secure its agreement, and in 1972 a further award of £650,000 for the costs of resettlement. A sum was also awarded to the plantation company. Payment to some of the Chagossians came later, by agreement between the UK and Mauritius.¹²

Perhaps some parties benefited from these payments, but nothing can disguise the fact that it was a clumsy and cruel operation that would leave deep scars. Not only was the removal of the population itself the core issue, but the manner in which it was carried out was underhand as well as callous. With the intention of blunting opposition in the UN, Britain maintained that there was no permanent population in the Chagos, only contract workers. The colonial power was well aware at the time that it was intentionally misleading the international body.¹³ It was hardly surprising that, for more than half a century, ‘human rights’ was something of a mantra to support the case against British actions. When the 2018 hearing opened in The Hague, the British counsel (no doubt wishing to deflect some obvious criticism) admitted that ‘it had treated the Chagossians very badly at and around the time of their removal and it deeply regrets that fact’.¹⁴

This admission was, of course, not enough to mute the inevitable attacks on its actions, and over the years human rights have been repeatedly highlighted as a critical issue. In a very detailed report, the eponymous NGO, Human Rights Watch, lambasted both the British and Americans for their actions. Instances of needless cruelty and abuse were highlighted and it would be folly to deny that these occurred. Given that all this happened so recently, over the past six decades culminating in the pronouncement of the International Court of Justice in 2019, the wounds are still open.

At the same time, it would be wrong to accept the argument totally at face value. A wrong was undoubtedly done, but were all aspects of the process as bad as described and were there no beneficial outcomes? NGOs have a job to do, and in this case the whole rationale for Human Rights Watch is to demonstrate that one group was abused by another. That was certainly the case but a reading of their report leaves one with unanswered questions. Based on interviews with 43 Chagossians in Mauritius, Seychelles and the UK, the report is presented as a totally one-sided account of events, which only serves to weaken the argument. In all that has happened, is it possible that there were no humane officials engaged in the resettlement process? Was the former life of the plantation workers and their families really as idyllic as the report and others now make out? Is the present generation, especially the younger members, actually intent on returning to a lifestyle without all the trappings they are now used to? If they were to return, where will the money come from to provide an infrastructure fit for inhabitants in the twenty-first century? And how much is the vexed question of reparations fuelling the continuing campaign to return? Even Philippe Sands, in his otherwise excellent book, puts (in my view) too much evidence on the story of one survivor of the resettlement. Her presence in The Hague might have made a telling courtroom impact but it hardly speaks for the many Chagossians who have found new opportunities elsewhere.

The fact remains, however, that the official British approach lacked any obvious humanity. Whether or not people would really want to return to Chagos, it is understandable that there will always be an interest and, indeed, an emotional attachment, to what is still regarded as

the ancestral homeland. The more this is denied, the more the tropical islands are recalled as an idyll. It is quite natural to look at the past through rose-tinted spectacles. In a recent study of the Chinese community in Seychelles, for instance, the importance of this kind of connection was apparent amongst everyone interviewed, and voluntary visits have invariably been made to villages where their families came from.¹⁵ But in not a single case did anyone trade in what they now have for what was left behind. Recently, the British authorities have organized ‘heritage visits’ to enable Chagossians to see for themselves the islands their families once knew. This is a late admission that these things do matter and, had this been done earlier, some of the heat of the argument might well have been reduced.

In any case, lurking beneath the surface, one cannot help but question whether this is really the issue that has motivated successive Mauritian governments to persevere in their claim to restore the original boundaries? Human rights represent a seductive issue when seeking international support, but surely the real reasons for persisting with the argument have a more material foundation. The fact is that Chagos offers rich pickings that go well beyond the historic lure of coconut plantations. By winning the argument, the Mauritian economy would receive a very significant boost. My own view is that, in private, human rights are barely likely to figure any longer in these calculations. There is, almost certainly, more to the issue than sometimes seems to be the case.

Hidden treasure

The Indian Ocean is a natural hunting ground for hidden treasure. Ships laden with precious cargoes have for centuries charted a course across the vast sea, attracting the unwanted attention of pirates and other adventurers or simply running aground in bad weather. There is hardly a bay in the ocean’s remote islands without a romantic tale of long-forgotten chests filled with gold and priceless gems. But, in the case of Chagos, it is the treasure within plain sight that holds better prospects for the modern-day opportunist. Look not to the fiction of hidden wealth but, instead, to a sea that is rich in its fisheries, islands that will attract elite tourism, and a seabed that is strewn with valuable metals. All of that is surely the real lure of these remote islands.

Thus, one obvious reason why Mauritius will stand to gain from a transfer of sovereign rights is that the sea around the archipelago offers lucrative opportunities for commercial fishing. In the regular visits to Chagos to allow parties of exiles to visit their lost homeland, one thing commonly reported is that, on approaching the islands, the waters are teeming with marine life. Unfortunately, this valuable resource suffers from a high incidence of illegal fishing. It is not only the volume of catches in these waters that is affecting the ecosystem but also the wide range of species that is being depleted. Although the Exclusive Economic Zone should, in

law, be immune from this activity, the level of surveillance is practically non-existent. The BIOT has at its disposal a chartered offshore vessel, the *Grampian Endurance*, to patrol an area the size of Texas.¹⁶ From time to time, a Royal Navy patrol ship might visit the area to offer assistance. In consequence, it is reported that:

*... over the past two years there has been a major increase in illegal fishing... Researchers who have been working in the territory for years have observed a significant decline in several keystone species, notably sharks. The levels of fishing are unprecedented.*¹⁷

Even if it becomes a protected area under Mauritian jurisdiction the question of effective security will remain a paramount issue. Relying on the odd patrol vessel is insufficient in the face of well-organized criminal encroachment. These fisheries will be of immense value to Mauritius – ecologically as well as commercially – but they also come at a price.

A second attraction in transferring the islands to Mauritius lies in their tourism potential. In spite of the neighbouring military base, with its attendant noise and military traffic, the rest of the islands will surely become a new venue for an exclusive form of maritime tourism. Access will be difficult for conventional aircraft but the idea of a tropical paradise that has escaped development for more than half a century will create niche opportunities for a unique experience. Its undisturbed outer islands will quickly find themselves on the global tourism map, leading to a predictable pattern of high-end resorts and marinas. The sea will be the star attraction, with its abundant fish, clear waters and exceptional biodiversity. Mauritius is well-versed in managing tourism and will be quick to make the most of this virgin territory.

Finally, there is the early prospect of seabed mining in the surrounding waters. Deep-ocean mining is a highly contentious topic and currently licences awarded by the International Seabed Authority are restricted to exploration in the high seas.¹⁸ Within EEZ boundaries, however, extraction can go ahead, subject only to domestic laws. Most international interest in this new form of mining is in the Pacific but the central Indian Ocean (close to and including Chagos) is attracting growing attention as a rich source of rare earth metals and minerals. Mauritius is already preparing domestic legislation to provide a framework for mining, and will probably need to partner with a larger nation like India (which already has a licence to explore what is there) to enable the substantial investment required to exploit its new reserves. So long as Britain retained sovereignty of the archipelago, Mauritius was precluded from direct involvement; but all that will now change. The question is whether deep-sea mining will be approached with sensitivity, given that so little is known about the ecological implications, or whether (as environmentalists fear) it will take on the characteristics of a nineteenth-century gold rush. The recent treaty on marine biodiversity offers some hope that actions will be consistent with the former option.¹⁹

Prevailing geopolitics

For all its inherent cultural and natural qualities, Chagos would not be in the news were it not for geopolitics. It has emerged as an item of interest as a result of erratic diplomacy on the part of Britain, combined with American pressure to locate a base in the region. One might have thought that issues of such magnitude are the subject of careful thought and consistent strategies but, in this case, there is scant evidence to support that.

The present dilemma of Chagos actually started in the neighbouring (though still distant) colony of Seychelles, where, in the 1960s Britain set its sights on the outer island of Aldabra to meet its own strategic needs in the region and to curry favour with its American ally.²⁰ Various plans were mooted, all of which involved the building of a runway across the atoll. In selecting Aldabra, Britain discovered only too late that there was already growing international interest in its unique environmental features. So, in the face of an effective campaign, supported by scientific evidence, it decided to cut its losses and quietly withdrew the plan. Attention then shifted eastwards, across a few thousand kilometres of open sea to Chagos and, within that, to the largest island, Diego Garcia. That was what the US had favoured in the first place, as part of what it called its 'strategic island concept'.²¹ The 58 islands in the archipelago together cover only 56 square kilometres of land and, of that, Diego Garcia occupies 32.5; the second-largest island is barely more than 3.1 square kilometres. Although America would only occupy the one island, there were concerns that the rest might one day be under the jurisdiction of Mauritius and that the ideological leanings of future governments could conceivably present problems. Hence, the decision by Britain (as the then 'landlord'), with the connivance of the Americans, to remove all of the 1500 inhabitants. In 1966, a 50-year lease was granted for the US base, known as Naval Support Facility Diego Garcia (also known, with what was surely a sense of irony, as Camp Justice), with the option of extending the lease by a further 20 years to 2036.²²

The location of Diego Garcia was not ideal – a distance of some 5000 kilometres from the Middle East and Western Asia – but it would serve as a base for a rapid airborne deployment force and a large naval fleet. It had within its range the strategically vulnerable oil supply routes and also Iran. When the Cold War ended in the last decade of the twentieth century, there were new issues to address. After 9/11, Afghanistan and northern Pakistan were also areas of interest and, so too, from 2003, attention was focused on Iraq. The base served a further purpose and it is believed that some high-level terrorists were brought there for questioning (something which the Americans and British have always denied). Amidst a high level of secrecy, year on year, the base has been enlarged and modernized to accommodate the latest weaponry. So long as the other islands of Chagos remained deserted, there was no risk of casual observation of what was taking place.

The deal to use the island was struck by the two allied forces behind closed doors.²³ Mauritius was at that time still a colony and when it was belatedly informed of the plan, it argued for a lease to be granted for the use of Diego Garcia rather than the creation of a new colony. It only relented under duress, when it is believed that Britain threatened to delay independence for Mauritius if it was not prepared to agree terms.²⁴ If the immediate goal was achieved, Britain was keenly aware that this would not be the end of it. In the words of then Colonial Secretary, Anthony Greenwood:

*Chagos would be added to the list of imperialist measures for which we are attacked, and of creating a new colony in a period of decolonization and of establishing new military bases when we should be getting out of the old ones.*²⁵

In one thing, Britain made a correct judgement, namely, the Chagos decision was riven with duplicity and the colonial power would not quickly be forgiven. If the sun was setting on the British Empire, it was not the tranquil kind of sunset that might have been hoped for.

When the 50-year lease ended in 2016, there was renewed opposition to America's presence on the disputed island. But, by then, in spite of the ending of the Cold War, a new pattern of strategic confrontation was forming. Particularly from the start of the present century, China was extending its naval reach into the Indian Ocean. Ostensibly to protect its growing trade links in the region, the move was widely interpreted as evidence of the East Asian power coming of age. When a new military base was established in Djibouti (close to the existing US presence in the Horn of Africa) any lingering doubts about China's intentions were set aside. The People's Republic of China was now a force to be reckoned with in the Indian Ocean and, in this context, America was even less likely than before to vacate its base in Chagos. To add to a perceived need to respond in kind, a strategic rethink led to the designation of the Indo-Pacific in place of, simply the Indian Ocean. Far from agreeing to leave Diego Garcia, America would need to strengthen its presence in the wider region. A long lease from Mauritius would enable the US to stay in place and, in recognizing the new sovereignty, it would curry favour in the international community – as one observer points out, resulting in a rare case of 'right' making 'might'.²⁶

Environmental matters

The environment of the Chagos archipelago has so far been presented as a backcloth to matters of state. But it is, of course, a key player in itself, an exceptional group of tropical islands left largely undisturbed for more than half a century. 'Largely' but not 'completely': the anomaly, of course, being the presence of a military base in the midst of the archipelago. Yet, even with that, the outer islands and surrounding expanse of ocean are unique in

themselves. If not, literally, pristine, most of the area cannot be far from the overworked myth of paradise. And, to add to its attraction, it is beyond the reach of cyclones which have a devastating impact on islands further south.²⁷ It is certainly a very special place and of importance not only to the sovereign power but, for its special qualities, to the rest of the world.

It was on the strength of this that Britain, in 2010, argued that Chagos should be designated in the form of a vast (640,000 square kilometres) Marine Protected Area, extending well beyond the Exclusive Economic Zone.²⁸ The idea was proposed in 2010 but, whatever its intrinsic merits, it was by then too enmeshed in the territorial dispute affecting the colony to be accepted by the international community. Given its secret dealings with America, Britain could no longer be trusted and the proposal was seen as a new form of colonial control under a different name. Questions were asked about the legality of the initiative and the effect it would have on allowing former inhabitants to return to the islands. After five years, amidst controversy, the proposal was formally withdrawn. In fact, as an environmental measure, it was in itself well founded and the reserve would have made a significant contribution to the global aim of protecting 30% of the world's seas in this way. It would on its own have doubled the global coverage of MPAs. Geopolitics, however, accounted for its demise at the time. But is there a chance that the idea of a protected area, if not all of the original management details, could at some stage be revived?

All the signs are that Chagos will soon be formally recognized as part of the sovereign state of Mauritius. There is a legally undeniable case for doing this. But rather than retreating behind the mantle of sovereignty, it is to be hoped that Mauritius will see this as an opportunity to serve global interests as well as its own. In the new geopolitical arena, where any semblance of colonial control will be consigned to the past, surely there is a chance of reviving the idea of a mid-ocean protected area – a tropical counterpart to the protected wilderness of the ice-bound south? It would be a statement of good intent. As a sign of a progressive state with green credentials, it would surely be to the advantage of Mauritius to take a lead in a new initiative of this kind.

Lingering questions

For what are mere dots on the world map, Chagos (which probably few people could locate) has found itself at the centre of a web of interconnecting themes of global importance: colonial and post-colonial, human rights and environmental protection, international law and geopolitics. It is difficult to be totally objective, although some themes are less contentious than others. Thus:

- ◆ The transition from a colonial to post-colonial era was on a clear and sensible trajectory, and one can only wonder how Britain decided to create a new colony in 1965. By that time, the rest of its empire was looking towards (or had already achieved) independence. The BIOT was an anachronism that beggars belief. Somewhere, in the musty offices along Whitehall there will have been officials who had long ago joined the colonial service but had not noticed that the world had since moved on.
- ◆ Human rights are less straightforward, immaculate in principle yet open to devious interpretations. In the case of Chagos, lawyers and others have played this card, in my view, to excess. However inexcusable it was to expel the inhabitants from their homes – something for which they should have been properly compensated and better assisted in finding new homes and jobs – I remain unconvinced that subsequent generations would choose to return to the basic conditions that would now await them; a heritage visit is one thing, a permanent change of lifestyle quite another.
- ◆ The wonderful environment – the sea as well as the islands – is in need of protection, a readymade wilderness to be cherished. It was a sad run of events which caused the proposed creation of what would have been the world's largest MPA to be abandoned. So opposed were some parties of anything that smacked of colonial authority, that even the fact that the well-respected Nature Conservancy was based in the US was used as a reason to reject the scheme. Once the dust settles on current negotiations, it is to be hoped that the new sovereign power will seek to reinstate the proposed MPA, albeit under different rules and personnel.
- ◆ International law is essential to a new global order. And yet, as the case of Chagos reveals, it is incredibly complex and too often seen as a means of preventing rather than enabling certain events. Outcomes depend as much on the disposition of those who sit in judgement as on the wording of the laws. The book by Philippe Sands that I refer to earlier is a revelation in this respect, although I remain at odds with his totemic use of former inhabitants to sway the courts.
- ◆ Finally, there is the quagmire of geopolitics, in which nothing is done without mutual favours. During the Cold War, Britain was unprincipled in its obeisance to the US, and in its secret deals lost respect in the international forum. Was it right to agree so readily to a military base in the Indian Ocean? Quite apart from the environmental damage done, any assessment depends on whether one believes that military force of this magnitude is necessary to keep the peace.

Chagos, as the above shows, generates numerous questions, for most of which there are no easy answers. But if they were easy, they would already have been answered. The status of the islands will change but it will almost certainly continue to be more newsworthy than the diminutive size of the territory might suggest.

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Notes and references

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<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0921818111002098>

²⁸ 'Marine Protected Area', British Indian Ocean Territory, n.d. <https://biot.gov.io/environment/marine-protected-area/>

Emeritus Professor Dennis Hardy graduated with a B.A (Hons.) in Geography from the University of Exeter, UK, followed by an MA in Geography by research. From there he joined the Greater London Council and qualified at University College London as a professional urban planner, in due course becoming a Fellow of the Royal Town Planning Institute. He obtained his PhD through part-time research in urban planning history at the London School of Economics and in 1988 was awarded a professorship at Middlesex University London. With a series of well-received books to his name, research and writing remain important elements of his profile. He is currently a research professor in the James R. Mancham Peace and Diplomacy Research Institute at the University of Seychelles, and he chairs the Council of the University of Seychelles.